

Enabling Live Video Provenance and Authenticity: A C2PA-Based System with TPM-Based Security for Livestreaming Platforms

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Abstract—The growing spread of misinformation in recent years has become a concern for both governments and citizens, highlighting the need to verify the origin, authenticity and history of media files. This relevant information, commonly referred to as provenance, provides media consumers with assurance that the content originates from a known and trusted source and has not been tampered with. To address the challenge of misinformation, the Coalition for Content Provenance and Authenticity (C2PA) has standardized the certification of media authenticity and provenance. While C2PA defines embedding standards for various media, it lacks specifications for live video streaming with provenance data. To bridge this gap, we propose a live video streaming system that incorporates the C2PA manifest data. The proposed solution is based on the HTTP Live Streaming (HLS) protocol for transmitting live video content, and uses the C2PA Software Development Kit (SDK) to generate and embed metadata at the source to be verified at the client-side backend. Our solution also relies on a hardware Trusted Platform Module (TPM) as a Secure Element (SE) to sign the manifest data. It is demonstrated that the use of a TPM ensures strong authenticity and attestation while introducing minimal delay to the video streaming pipeline. Finally, we also explore how this technology could be integrated into livestreaming services like Twitch to allow viewers to verify that the stream is trustworthy, while simultaneously providing content creators with protection against content manipulation and copyright infringement.

Index Terms—C2PA, Hardware Security, HTTP Live Streaming, Live Video Streaming, Media Provenance, Trusted Platform Module.

I. INTRODUCTION

IN recent years, the rapid evolution of artificial intelligence (AI) has brought significant breakthroughs in different fields, but it has also introduced new challenges: the rise and proliferation of fake news and convincing images, video and audio, all obtained by generative AI, can deceive unsuspecting viewers. For example, deepfake technology can manipulate and create fake videos or convincing audios of prominent

politicians, which can be used to spread misinformation or propaganda, manipulating public opinion, swaying voting intention, or sparking social unrest [1], [2]. In order to combat misinformation, the Coalition for Content Provenance and Authenticity (C2PA) is defining a standard to ensure the authenticity of the media, its provenance, as well as a history of modifications or any other relevant information within a tamper-evident structure [3]. This structure is embedded into the media by its producer, and any compatible client can extract this information, verify its authenticity and integrity, and therefore determine whether the content comes from a trusted source and what authorized modifications it has suffered (if any). If the client expects C2PA metadata to be embedded in the media, but it is either invalid or missing when received, then the media is assumed to have suffered unauthorized modification and its content may have been tampered with. C2PA is already supported in some platforms and applications. For example, Adobe Photoshop can work with images containing a C2PA manifest [4]. YouTube also provides support for C2PA manifests embedded in uploaded videos [5]. Last, both generative AI for images from OpenAI and Adobe (Dall-E and Firefly, respectively) add this provenance information to images they generate [6]. It is important to note that this method is not foolproof: the metadata might be stripped off by some applications, corrupted during transfer, or completely removed if the media is captured via a screenshot or video recording. In this paper, we explore the use of C2PA for ensuring live video authenticity and provenance. For that, a video stream is generated in real time, encoded, and then signed with the C2PA Software Development Kit (SDK) to embed the corresponding C2PA metadata. The resulting media is made available to clients through a video server. On the client side, a web application connects to the server, streams the content, and verifies in real time whether the video’s authenticity and provenance are preserved or if the metadata has been removed or altered due to a malicious attack. Therefore, a C2PA enabled live video system based on the HLS standard has been implemented, which includes the media producer and the consumer. For the signature of the media files, a Trusted Platform Module (TPM) has been used. Measurements of the signing time and delay produced by the use of this Secure Element (SE) have been obtained, as well as a comparison with other cryptographic implementations, both software and hardware based, which highlights the balance obtained with the TPM between speed and key protection. The manuscript is organized as follows. Section II provides a literature review on how metadata is typically added or embedded in the media and why these methods fail to guarantee authenticity and

This work was supported by Infineon Technologies AG. Additional funding was provided by the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme Project EDGELESS, under Grant Agreement No. 101092950, Project SHIELD under Grant Agreement No. 101214779 as well as by the Junta de Andalucía – Consejería de Universidad, Investigación e Innovación through the project ProyExcel_00268. *Corresponding author:* Francisco J. Romero.

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provenance. Following this assessment, Section III presents the most relevant aspects of the C2PA standard including the structures embedded in the media and how they are uniquely linked to the corresponding file via cryptographic proofs and signatures. In Section IV, the system architecture is introduced with a high-level overview, followed by a detailed explanation of the specific technical implementation. Since the video needs to be generated and signed with minimal delay to enable live streaming, the delay introduced by the cryptographic signature required for the C2PA manifest is also analyzed to ensure it does not significantly affect latency. Section V includes the experimental results, where the overhead introduced by C2PA in terms of both processing time and storage requirements is also studied. Finally, Section VI discusses compatible platforms and potential integrations in livestreaming services like Twitch, highlighting the potential benefits of C2PA metadata in improving the user experience and protecting content creators.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Embedded metadata in the media provides both the consumers and producers with relevant information about the content. For instance, embedded metadata in a picture can contain the coordinates of where the picture was taken, a timestamp, as well as information of the camera configuration used, such as focal distance, ISO or aperture. Typically, this metadata is embedded in the media using well-supported standards like the Exchangeable image file (Exif) format, which defines the information that can be embedded on the media [7]. However, Exif metadata is vulnerable to manipulation, as it can be easily modified by an attacker to alter the embedded information. Exif metadata also introduces some privacy concerns, since geotags and timestamps can expose the user location and activities, especially if shared online [8]. Moreover, Exif metadata does not provide any proof of authenticity, origin or history (provenance) of the media. An alternative to embedded metadata is the use of watermarks, which display relevant information directly on top of the current image. However, although watermarks are more resistant to tampering, they obscure parts of the image, making them less than ideal for many use cases. Regarding provenance data, the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C) PROV standard defines a model, serializations and definitions to enable the interoperable exchange of provenance information. It captures how entities (webpages, images, and charts) are created and how they evolve over time through various activities. These activities are carried out by agents, which can be individuals, software applications, or organizations [9]. However, the PROV standard does not specify how provenance data can be uniquely linked to an entity to prevent tampering. Some solutions address this limitation by leveraging blockchain technology: once PROV data is recorded on a blockchain, its cryptographic properties ensure immutability, making it resistant to unauthorized modifications. [10]. Other alternatives exist to provide authentication to the media being consumed, or relevant information about the origin and provenance of it. This includes blockchain based approaches like the Vbrik Verified Authentic, which combines the C2PA manifest with blockchain to provide strong assurance and tamper-proof capabilities. However, depending on

the blockchain chosen (e.g., Ethereum, Bitcoin, Hyperledger Fabric), there might be gas fees or long delays associated with the transactions performed to add the C2PA information to the blockchain. There is also professional software like Magnet Verify, designed as a forensic tool that maintains and verifies the provenance and chain of custody, as well as other forensic tools based on Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) designed to detect what modifications an image suffered and in which order [11]. However, these types of solutions are geared towards static images and forensic use, not for mass adoption by the public. Some work has been developed on the use of invisible watermarking on the media which is even resistant to screenshots or images taken from screens [12] [13]. These approaches are useful at detecting unauthorized leaks of information in industrial settings, as the image has an invisible fingerprint that is not visible to the user, and that can be persistent even with heavy modifications of the image. This approach, already considered by the C2PA specification in the soft binding section, could prove useful to embed the remote address of a manifest directory that could help in recovering the provenance data even when an attacker has removed the embedded manifest. The C2PA does have a list of allowed watermarking algorithms, which includes for example Adobe Trustmark [14]. A comparison of the mentioned mechanisms can be seen in Table S1.

In an age with an increasing use of AI imaging tools that can generate realistic images, verifying media authenticity and provenance is crucial in combating disinformation. This is where C2PA comes into play. The C2PA standard defines a manifest containing relevant information about the media, which is embedded and cryptographically signed to bind the metadata to the specific media file. In this way, any unauthorized modification to the media or its manifest can be easily detected and reported to the user thanks to the C2PA verification. In order to provide this authenticity and provenance information, the C2PA introduces key terms and structures defined in the *C2PA Manifest Store* [15], which is shown in Fig. 1.

The *C2PA Manifest Store* is a collection of *Manifests* that are embedded into the media asset. A *Manifest* is the set of information about the provenance of an asset, and it is based on one or more *Assertions*, a single *Claim*, and a *Claim Signature*. *Assertions* are data structures representing statements made or created concerning the asset. For example, assertions can be metadata from the camera manufacturer, media editing (such as color correction), or cryptographic hashes that represent content binding. *Claims* are digitally signed data structures that reference a set of assertions for an asset, along with information related to content binding. Lastly, the *Claim Signature* is a digital signature applied to the claim using a private key. The signing process begins by hashing the data with one of the allowed algorithms specified in the C2PA standard. The accepted signing algorithms include Elliptic Curve Digital Signature Algorithm (ECDSA), Rivest–Shamir–Adleman signature Scheme with Appendix (RSASSA), as well as Edwards-curve Digital Signature Algorithm (EdDSA). The signature is generated for the Concise Binary Object Representation (CBOR) encoded claim using the CBOR Object Signing

Fig. 1. C2PA Manifest Store [15].

and Encryption (COSE) [16], [17]. During the verification process, the active manifest is retrieved from the media, and both signature and embedded information are checked. The verification process may return one of the following results:

- 1) Well-formed: the manifest is correct and follows the normative requirements of the C2PA specification.
- 2) Valid: the manifest is well-formed, it has not been modified after the signature, and the claim signature is verified.
- 3) Trusted: the manifest is well-formed, valid, and the signing credentials are trusted by the device.

If the verification process fails at any point, then the manifest is considered invalid, and the user is notified. C2PA supports the use of a counter signature from a trusted time-stamping authority to prove that the signature existed at a specific date and time and that it was incorporated to the media [18]. Without a counter-signature, the manifest becomes invalid once the associated certificate expires or is revoked, potentially limiting the long-term relevance of the provenance data.

The Content Authenticity Initiative, which promotes the C2PA standard within the industry, recommends the use of a Hardware Security Module (HSM) or Key Management System (KMS) to manage the key used to sign the manifest [19]. Although both of these solutions aim to produce the same result, i.e., the claim signature in the manifest store, small differences make each one them more appropriate for

one particular application or another. For instance, compact and low-power HSMs are often preferred in IoT applications to maximize battery life and minimize device footprint. Online KMS services are ideal for cloud-based media generation, such as generating images with AI tools, while security keys can be advantageous when the identity is tied to a physical person or organization. Examples of these solutions include Amazon KMS, Yubico Security Keys, Infineon OPTIGA™ Trust M, Trusted Platform Modules (TPMs), as well as Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs) like Intel Software Guard Extensions (SGX), each offering different degrees of security and adaptability depending on the use case. In this case, the focus is on the use of a TPM, as it offers a distinct advantage over other implementations by providing attestation for the media, thus allowing a device to prove its identity and security status [20].

The C2PA framework distinguishes two types of attestation: implicit and explicit. *Implicit attestation*, as defined in the C2PA specification, refers to the ability of the recipient of C2PA media to implicitly verify that the media originates from a trusted source and an unmodified device, provided that the signature is valid, the certificate is unique and signed by a trusted Certificate Authority (CA), and the private key is securely stored. These requirements are all fulfilled through the use of a TPM. Furthermore, in *Explicit Attestation*, the signature is performed using a special Attestation Key (AK), which combines application data with measurements of the software environment. This process, commonly referred to as quoting, is commonly used for device attestation. In that case, the software status is extended into the TPM's Platform Configuration Registers (PCRs), ensuring that the TPM quote reflects the actual status of the running software [21]. A security analysis of the C2PA specification as well as the TPM as the Claim Signer can be consulted in the Supporting Information.

In this case, the focus is on the Implicit Attestation. A device that integrates a TPM already has a platform key and certificate, like the Endorsement Key (EK), which uniquely identifies the TPM, or the AK, which can be derived from the EK and can be generated for a specific application. Using this set of keys, a device can be enrolled onto a trusted service, and an application certificate and key can be generated and provisioned onto the TPM. When a C2PA Claim Creator is installed on the device, it can use this information to sign the manifest. Security can be further enhanced by applying sealing and unsealing mechanisms [22], where the TPM will only sign data if the PCRs are at specific values (e.g., after a secure boot sequence is completed). Note that this attestation could also be provided by TEEs like ARM TrustZone or Intel SGX, although this latter one has been deprecated on client-oriented hardware [23].

Regarding video streaming, given the multiple ways in which video files are consumed, multiple standards can be found for transmitting these files from media producers to consumers. Each standard introduces different delays, video encoding methods, quality levels and compression techniques. This discussion focuses on two protocols commonly used for live video streaming: Dynamic Adaptive Streaming over HTTP

```

#EXTM3U
#EXT-X-VERSION:3
#EXT-X-TARGETDURATION:11
#EXT-X-MEDIA-SEQUENCE:0
#EXTINF:11.208333,
playlist0.ts
#EXTINF:10.416667,
playlist1.ts
#EXTINF:10.416667,
playlist2.ts
#EXTINF:10.416667,
playlist3.ts
#EXTINF:10.416667,

```

Fig. 2. Example of M3U8 HLS playlist file content.

(DASH) and HTTP Live Streaming (HLS) [24], [25]. Both protocols rely on HTTP for video transmission, which provides several advantages. Since HTTP traffic is typically not blocked by firewalls unlike other protocols such as Real-Time Protocol (RTP), it ensures easier delivery of the video content. Additionally, the internet infrastructure is highly optimized for HTTP traffic through the use of Content Delivery Networks (CDNs), edge caching, and other techniques, enabling efficient bandwidth usage while simultaneously providing services to many concurrent users. Both DASH and HLS protocols work by dividing the video feed into small chunks of video of variable length, typically between 2 and 10 seconds. The video files are transmitted using HTTP over TCP. Apart from the video files, DASH sends a Media Presentation Description (MPD) file while HLS uses an extended M3U playlist file [26], [27]. Both of these files contain information regarding segment information, such as their timing, duration, URL, media characteristics (e.g., resolution, bit rates) and more. An example of an M3U playlist file as used in HLS is presented in Fig. 2, which shows the duration and order of each media segment, as well as the playlist version (v3) and instructions to start playback with segment number 0.

This information is crucial for the client to be able to obtain and parse the video files in order to present them to the user in a seamless way. In both cases, a server generates the video files, encodes the video in compatible formats like H.264 or H.265, and then encapsulates the video in MPEG-2 Transport Stream (TS), MPEG-4 or BMFF ISO media, although the latter one is used exclusively in DASH. Both the video files and their corresponding description files are made available on the server. Therefore, the client simply connects, downloads the video files, and a compatible video player assembles them using the description file to manage playback and download sequences. While these two standards are very similar, DASH is an open standard while HLS is proprietary from Apple Inc. However, this later one is the de facto standard due to its broader support and widespread implementation. It is important to note that live video streaming with C2PA manifests is not possible when using DASH with BMFF ISO media. This limitation arises because, according to the C2PA specification, the manifest in BMFF media must be embedded in the initialization video file. Since the manifest

is overwritten every time the initialization fragment changes when a new video segment is added, the cryptographic proof in the previous manifest loses its validity, and the C2PA verification process fails [28].

Up until now, the C2PA specification has not defined a standard for binding manifests to live video. However, some implementations that suggest how this might be done in the future have emerged, despite not being fully compliant with the current specification. One example is the media signing specification from the Open Network Video Interface Forum (ONVIF), which focuses on establishing open standards for IP-based security products such as security cameras [29]. In this case, the device generating the video embeds the signature and metadata in the Supplemental Enhancement Information (SEI) fields. Hashes are generated for Groups of Pictures (GOPs), which consist of a set of video frames starting and ending with an I-frame (a full image), while the intermediate frames (P-frames and B-frames) are predicted from the adjacent frames. Since the P- and B-frames are linked to the I-frame, the hashes are generated in a connected manner, referencing the I-frame for the hashing. These hashes are collected into a document, which is then signed using the device's private key. The signature and document are then embedded into the SEI fields, allowing compatible clients to retrieve and verify them. Validation is performed GOP by GOP, where firstly the Root CA is obtained to verify the included certificate in the SEI. Secondly, the signatures and hashes are checked to confirm the authenticity of the video and detect any lost NAL units or unsigned content [30]. This approach introduces transmission delays and increases overhead, as the additional hashes for each P- and B-frame expand the document size, although Merkle trees could be used to reduce this overhead and speed up verification [31]. Moreover, the certificate required for verification is embedded in a special SEI field and may need to be sent periodically to accommodate new client connections, and clients cannot fully trust the content until the certificate is received. Additionally, when GOP durations are very short, there might not be enough time to sign and embed the information before transmission, causing some video segments to lack signature data. Therefore, the integration of C2PA metadata in an standard like ONVIF does not seem a feasible approach, showcasing that a more efficient solution is needed for embedding C2PA in live video.

In this direction, this paper presents the implementation of a live video streaming setup with minimal delay using the C2PA SDK and HLS. For that, a live video feed is encoded and encapsulated into short fragments of a few seconds each. After that, the video fragments are processed by the C2PA Claim Generator from the C2PA SDK to embed a manifest in each fragment and then served by an HLS server. A TPM is used as a secure key vault and to perform the required signature. Since the manifest is embedded in the video files, no special modifications on the server side are necessary. On the client side, a custom application connects to the server, downloads the video fragments, and verifies the validity of each manifest using the same SDK. The Graphical User Interface (GUI) has been developed following the Content Credentials design principles to visually inform users whether the media they

are viewing is trustworthy. This implementation could also be extended to DASH by modifying the segment information files and encoding format, as well as switching from the HLS to DASH libraries on the client side to perform the video playback. Our implementation focuses on the live video aspect, as well as the signing time of the C2PA manifest. While other published works regarding C2PA and video usually implement the GUI and client-side verification [28], or a full C2PA enabled system [32], their focus is on DASH with static videos that have the C2PA manifest embedded beforehand and are just streamed to the users. In addition, our implementation only considers the use of hard binding to detect tampering. Moreover, while other works also introduce the use of blockchain technology in tandem with the C2PA [33], this has not been considered by the C2PA specification, and would introduce too much delay in the live video pipeline.

III. FRAMEWORK

This section presents the key components that enable live video streaming as well as how the media provider generates the video feed and adds the C2PA manifest. It also describes the verification process that is performed on the client side and how the verification data are displayed to the user through the GUI.

A. Media Provider: Data Generation and C2PA Manifest Embedding.

The media provider generates a video stream that may come from a webcam, a connected camera, or the output of an editing program (e.g., a timestamp can be added via software, or the video may be a color-corrected before streaming). Provenance information for the video is collected, including details about the creator (if applicable), tools used for modification, the software and hardware involved in recording, and even GPS coordinates indicating where the video was captured. This information forms the C2PA manifest, which is embedded into the media asset, in this case, the video. MP4 files are structured using so-called "boxes", which organize and store different types of data. These typically include the File Type Header (ftyp), which identifies the file format, the Media Data Box (mdat), which contains the actual media track, and the Movie Box (moov), which holds metadata and other structural information. The C2PA specification introduces an additional "uuid" box, which embeds the manifest store. This box must be placed before the first "mdat" box and any "moov" box within the media file [34]. The manifest is cryptographically bound to the video as it contains a hash of the asset, allowing for tamper detection. In this context, each video segment is treated as independent from the previous and subsequent ones. The video stream from the camera is captured and encoded into an HLS video stream. Every few seconds (depending on the HLS segment size), a new MPEG-2 Transport Stream container is generated with its details added to the extended M3U playlist to ensure the user can access the new fragments. Once the video is stored in the container, the C2PA manifest is embedded into the media, with the manifest signed using the TPM. Since the manifest is embedded, synchronization between the media and the C2PA metadata is guaranteed.

Fig. 3. Scheme of the C2PA video provider

B. Media consumer: Provenance Check and User Notification.

The media consumer on the client side connects to the HLS server using a compatible browser and a webpage containing the necessary libraries for HLS video playback. The client's back-end automatically validates the C2PA information each time a new fragment is received and displays the relevant details to the user. If the manifest validation succeeds, the C2PA system returns a "validated" status, and the GUI updates showing key information from the fragment. If, on the contrary, the manifest validation fails, the user is immediately informed through a visual change in the GUI.

IV. TECHNICAL IMPLEMENTATION.

A. Media Provider.

As previously explained, HLS delivers small chunks of the video stream over HTTP along with an extended M3U playlist containing information about the available video streams. The overall architecture of the C2PA media provider is schematized in Fig. 3. The video source in this setup is the Raspberry Pi Camera V3, configured to produce a Full HD video stream (1920x1080 pixels) at 30 frames per second. The raw video is pipelined directly into FFmpeg, a suite of specialized C libraries that handle many video operations [35]. FFmpeg receives the raw video from the camera, packetizes it into MPEG-2 Transport Stream (.ts) segments of a predefined duration and updates the M3U playlist with the new chunk information. Since the camera's output is already encoded in H.264, there is minimal delay in generating the HLS fragments, avoiding the latency that re-encoding would typically require, especially in constrained or low-end hardware. When a new video fragment is generated, the C2PA manifest is automatically embedded into the media using the C2PA SDK, where the TPM is used for handling the signature process. In this setup, the TPM has been provisioned with a persistent key stored in its non-volatile memory, which is used for signing the manifest, along with a valid certificate. The corresponding certificate is also included in the manifest to facilitate the verification process on the client side. Finally, the modified video stream with the embedded C2PA manifest and the updated playlist are served to clients over HTTP using HLS.

B. Media Consumer.

On the client side, a compatible device is required to play the HLS video and display the C2PA information to the user.

Fig. 4. Scheme of the C2PA video consumer

It is important to note that the addition of the C2PA manifest does not impose any restrictions on media playback. Therefore, if the client device does not support C2PA metadata, the video would still play as long as the browser supports the necessary video libraries. In this case, the scheme of the C2PA video consumer is shown in Fig. 4. The client side consists of a custom-designed webpage where the HLS video is played, and an overlay displays the C2PA information when requested. Video playback is handled using the `hls.js` JavaScript library [36]. When video playback starts, the `FRAG_LOADING` event, which is triggered each time a fragment is being loaded, is used to initiate the process of verifying the C2PA manifest. During the validation process, both the signature generated with the TPM’s private key and the counter-signature from the timestamping service are checked, in accordance with the C2PA specification. If the manifest is successfully verified, the webpage’s GUI updates to indicate that the fragment is trustworthy with a green tick. In that case, the client can also access additional information from the manifest, such as the camera and software used to produce the video, the identity of the signer, and any modifications made to the video. If the C2PA manifest is missing or validation fails, the GUI reflects this status with a red cross.

C. Graphical User Interface.

As introduced before, the user interface is built using the `hls.js` library and follows the UI design principles from Content Credentials on how to present the data to the user [37]. Since this is a live video, a tick/cross icon was added to the Content Credential pin to concisely indicate the current state of the video. This corresponds to Level 1 disclosure, where the user can quickly determine at a glance whether the manifest is present and successfully validated. By clicking the Content Credential pin, a popup window is displayed, allowing the user to review a summary of the manifest data with enough information to describe how the asset reached its current state. The data includes details such as whether an effect was applied to the video, which camera and device were used to record it and information about the C2PA SDK version used to embed the metadata, corresponding to Level 2 disclosure. Fig. 5 shows the interface when the video manifest is successfully verified, displaying the embedded manifest information. In this example, a black-and-white filter was applied to the video, as indicated in the manifest. Moreover, Fig. 6 illustrates the results obtained for some of the different effects that were developed to be applied to the video on the

Fig. 5. C2PA GUI and embedded metadata for a valid video fragment.

media provider side, including an inverted color filter (a), a simulated attack scenario where the C2PA manifest was stripped from the video (b), and a video with a timestamp simulating a security camera feed (c). These filters capture the live video feed input from the camera, and perform frame-by-frame modifications using the OpenCV library.

D. Video Generation Pipeline.

The addition of the C2PA manifest could occur at different stages. For example, the video feed from the streamer’s webcam could directly include the C2PA metadata, while a similar system could be used for the audio from the microphone. In this case, the final C2PA video fragment would contain multiple different manifests in the Manifest Store, each referencing the individual components that make up the video feed. However, this approach does not provide a discernible benefit over embedding the C2PA manifest into the video after it has been generated and all the information has been embedded, especially if the platform’s security is robust enough to prevent any data modifications. On the server side, once the C2PA video has been received, it would be possible to verify the manifest, redact any private information, and then add another manifest with relevant details from the streaming service before providing the video fragments to the users. A diagram of the discussed C2PA enabled live video can be seen in Figure S3.

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS.

The C2PA specification recommends using a Hardware Security Module (HSM) or Key Management Service (KMS) for signing manifests to ensure strong security, key protection and compliance. In this case, the TPM is used as HSM for such purpose due to its tamper-resistant environment for securely managing cryptographic keys, minimizing the risk of unauthorized access or key compromise. In addition, it is optimized for high-frequency signing in real-time applications, making it a

Fig. 6. C2PA GUI and embedded metadata for video fragments with an inverse filter (a), a simulated attack (b), and a timestamped watermark (c).

Fig. 7. Media provider modules including the Raspberry Pi Camera V3 and the Infineon OPTIGA™ TPM SLB9672 Evaluation Expansion Board for Raspberry Pi.

perfect candidate for the target application. To demonstrate the feasibility of using a TPM without significantly impacting user experience, we evaluated the delay introduced by C2PA when signing live-streaming data. For that, a timing experiment was conducted to measure how long the TPM takes to sign the manifest using different approaches under the following conditions: Elliptic Curve Key prime256v1 (NIST P-256), ECDSA with SHA-256 as the signature algorithm, a 1.2 KB manifest size, 7 claims, and 100 repetitions.

The manifest embedded in the metadata contains the claim signature and claims, including information about the device that generated the video file, such as its model and manufacturer, camera data, device location, and the status of the video file, among other details. The TPM used in this experiment was the Infineon OPTIGA™ TPM SLB9672, running firmware version 16.10, which communicates with a Raspberry Pi over SPI at 33 MHz [38]. A Raspberry Pi 5 with 8GB of RAM, running the latest version of Raspbian OS 12 based on the Linux kernel v6.6, was used to execute the C2PA SDK v0.12.0 and handle communication with the TPM. The different modules are shown in Fig. 7.

The timing results correspond to the time required by the TPM and device to hash the data, perform the signature, and return the signed data over SPI. Additional delays caused by generating and embedding the manifest on the media can vary depending on factors such as CPU load, disk read/write speeds, and the size of the media file. The results for the different approaches are shown in Table I.

The *C2PA Rust* approach shown in Table I corresponds to

TABLE I
TIME REQUIRED FOR C2PA SIGNATURE USING DIFFERENT APPROACHES:
TPM IMPLEMENTATIONS, SOFTWARE BASED IMPLEMENTATIONS AND
OTHER SE

TPM implementation	Time taken (ms)
Go-TPM Lib Persistent Key	40.9 ± 0.9
Rust-TPM Lib Persistent Key	74 ± 5
Go-TPM Lib	138.4 ± 9.2
OpenSSL + TPM	486.6 ± 10.4
Software implementation	Time taken (ms)
Rust OpenSSL [39]	0.9 ± 0.8
Rust Crypto Lib [40]	7.4 ± 3.8
C2PA Rust	7.6 ± 1.1
OpenSSL CLI	42.4 ± 7.5
Other SE implementation	Time taken (ms)
Intel SGX TEE [41]	0.9
Apple Secure Enclave M4 SoC [42]	4.6 ± 0.1
STMicro TPM STM7364 Go-TPM [43]	47.5 ± 2.6
OPTIGA™ Trust M v3 [44]	63 ± 1

the time required by the Rust implementation of a signer, as provided by the C2PA SDK. Although this approach provides relatively low latency, it lacks hardware-based key protection mechanisms. Instead, the cryptographic key is stored in the system memory, making it vulnerable to theft by malicious attackers through techniques such as memory dumps or process inspection. Without a secure environment to protect the key, there is a higher risk of unauthorized access and key theft, which compromises the trustworthiness of the C2PA manifest. Alternatively, the C2PA SDK offers support for the use of external custom signers. The signers receive the claim bytes to be signed from the standard input, perform the signature and return the signed bytes to the standard output. In this way, we firstly tested the use of a software-based signature implementation based on OpenSSL as external signer (*OpenSSL CLI* in Table I), which resulted in a slower execution time, while still lacking hardware-based key protection. Despite this, one of the advantages of using OpenSSL is the possibility to configure the use of a TPM for cryptographic operations [45]. This provides enhanced security since the private key is securely stored and the operations are performed inside the TPM's protected environment. However, this approach, marked as *OpenSSL + TPM*, introduces a latency of almost

500 ms, making it unsuitable for live video streaming. This time was significantly reduced down to 138.4 ms using the *Go-TPM* library to interface the TPM with the TPM Software Stack (TSS) and the TPM Access Broker and Resource Manager (TPM-ABRMD) [46]. Additionally, this approach is also compatible with persistent key storage, where the key is persisted in the TPM’s non-volatile (NV) memory allowing the *Go-TPM* library to access it without having to regenerate or reload it every signature request. In that case, a delay of around 40 ms can be achieved (*Go-TPM Lib Persistent Key* in Table I), which is considered acceptable for live streaming devices, as it is significantly smaller than typical network latency and could be further optimized if multiple operations are stacked and properly pipelined [47], [48]. This approach requires almost half of the time compared with the persistent key approach using the *Rust-TPM* library [49]. Each custom signer using the TPM uses different APIs to access and interact with its functionality. The software stack for the TPM is shown in Fig. 8. The higher a component is in the hierarchy chain, the more abstracted the TPM’s functionality becomes, but at the cost of performance. This is the case of *OpenSSL + TPM* in Table I, which has the longest execution time due to accessing the TPM at the application level. In contrast, the *Go-TPM* signer is the fastest implementation, as it directly communicates with the TPM at a lower level using the System API (SAPI). Moreover, although the performance of the *Rust-TPM* library is relatively low, it is still higher due to its use of the Enhanced SAPI (ESAPI), as it requires establishing an encrypted session between the TPM and the device to perform a signature, hence introducing additional delays for encryption and decryption at both ends. Alternative software implementations as well as hardware SE were also measured using the same methodology to provide a comparison with the TPM. As shown, the signing time is minimized to around 1 ms when using the *OpenSSL* bindings for *Rust* library. This is an expected result, as *OpenSSL* is a mature and widely used cryptographic library, and thus highly optimized. However, this implementation does not benefit from the hardened key protection provided by a SE. Signing time was also measured with another TPM (*STMicro TPM STM7364*), which obtained slightly higher time than the chosen TPM. Another SE, the *OPTIGA™ Trust M v3* was also considered. In this case, the time increased by approximately 50% compared to the TPM solution. This increase is expected due to the slower I²C connection used, as well as the fact that the *OPTIGA™ Trust M* is optimized for low-power operation in IoT applications rather than for timing performance. For a Trusted Execution Environment (TEE), the Intel SGX signing times reported in the literature are similar to those obtained with the *Rust OpenSSL* implementation. While SGX could also provide attestation capabilities for the C2PA manifest, Intel deprecated its use on consumer hardware in 2022 [50], and it is not as widely available as the TPM, being limited to certain existing server architectures. Finally, the Secure Enclave in an Apple M4 processor was used to sign the data, achieving a low time of approximately 4.5 ms. While this is a competitive result, the closed-source firmware and proprietary documentation may conceal potential vulnerabilities, and support is restricted

Fig. 8. Trusted Computing Group TPM 2.0 Software Stack Design.

Fig. 9. Time required to sign the manifest for different video sizes.

exclusively to Apple devices.

To determine whether the time required for the TPM to sign increases with video size, the signing process using the C2PA SDK was measured across different video qualities and lengths, thus resulting in different video file sizes. The results are presented in Fig. 9. Since all video configurations use the same manifest to be embedded onto the media (1347 KB), the observed delay comes from the hashing process performed by the C2PA SDK to bind the video file to the manifest. An exponential increase in processing time is observed as the file size increases. This delay can be mitigated externally by using a lower bitrate, more efficient codecs that generate smaller files, or both. In our case, the video files remain below the 10MB threshold due to their short duration and efficient codec use, to avoid long delays in the transmission.

Furthermore, we also evaluated the delay introduced by the TPM during the signing process. For that, manifests of various sizes were generated and embedded into the video files. The results for each manifest size, averaged over 100 iterations, are presented in Table II. This time corresponds to the signing time

TABLE II

TIME REQUIRED BY THE TPM PERSISTENT KEY IMPLEMENTATION IN BOTH RUST AND GO FOR SIGNING DIFFERENT MANIFEST SIZES.

Manifest (B)	Rust-TPM (ms)	Go-TPM (ms)
100	94 ± 7	40 ± 1
1K	98 ± 7	40 ± 1
10K	96 ± 6	40 ± 1
100K	110 ± 3	40 ± 1
1M	190 ± 3	45 ± 3
10M	1023 ± 58	88 ± 7
100M	9206 ± 92	473 ± 36

TABLE III

TIME TAKEN FOR THE C2PA VERIFICATION ON THE CLIENT

Manifest Size (B)	Time (ms)
1K	14 ± 1
10K	16 ± 1
100K	19 ± 1
1M	43 ± 3
10M	309 ± 5

and the additional delay introduced by the hashing process performed in software. As observed, the signing time for the GO implementation remains consistent around 40 ms. This is expected, as the TPM only performs the signature over a SHA-256 hashed dataset. However, the total signing time, including hashing, exhibits an exponential increase as the manifest size grows over 1MB. However, it is unlikely for a video file to contain a manifest larger than 1MB (it would be equivalent to 500 pages of plain text). These time results are around a half of those obtained for the Rust TPM implementation when small manifest sizes are considered, while for large manifest sizes the hashing function introduces much higher delays. In our case, we used a manifest size of around 1KB.

The time required for the C2PA SDK to verify the manifest was also measured. This delay is critical, as a high verification time could negatively impact the user experience by delaying the confirmation of whether the media can be trusted. For this experiment, the verification time was measured 100 times for different manifest sizes. The values obtained are shown in Table III. For the verification process, the hash is recalculated for the media, and the signed hash is compared. The C2PA performs the different verifications previously mentioned. Note that this process uses the public key to validate the signature, so the use of the TPM is not required. Similar to previous measurements, the verification time remains stable for manifest sizes up to 1 MB, increasing rapidly beyond that size. Since the typical manifest size for embedding is well below 10 KB, the verification delay is negligible in most practical scenarios.

Furthermore, it is also important to evaluate the percentage that the C2PA manifest represents on the overall media file size. For that, we measured the percentage of the C2PA manifest in the generated media files for different video segment lengths. These measurements were performed under the same conditions as described earlier, with 100 repetitions using the same manifest file. The experiment was repeated for three different segment durations (one, two, and three seconds) using the same H.264 encoder for consistency.

TABLE IV

PERCENTAGE OF THE VIDEO FILE OCCUPIED BY THE C2PA MANIFEST FOR DIFFERENT VIDEO LENGTHS.

Video Length (s)	Video Size (MB)	Manifest Size (%)
1.0 ± 0.1	1.42 ± 0.08	1.2 ± 0.8
2.0 ± 0.1	3.3 ± 0.4	0.63 ± 0.02
3.0 ± 0.1	4.88 ± 0.12	0.40 ± 0.01

TABLE V

COMPARISON OF EXECUTION TIME DEPENDING ON THE STORAGE DEVICE

Video Length (s)	Device used	Execution time (ms)
3	SSD	426.29 ± 9.07
3	SD Card	427.51 ± 33.98
10	SSD	914.90 ± 32.27
10	SD Card	949.85 ± 56.63

The results, presented in Table IV, demonstrated that the percentage of the video that the manifest represents decreases as the the duration of the video increases. Even for short videos, the C2PA manifest represents barely 1% of the total video size, although it is important to note that such short durations are not typically used in production. In addition, it is also important to consider that this percentage depends on the codec and resolution used. For example, if a more advanced codec with higher compression is applied, the resulting video will be smaller, and the manifest will occupy a larger percentage of the file [51]. However, advanced codecs may require longer encoding times, so it is up to developers to choose the best combination of encoding settings to minimize the manifest’s impact without compromising video quality or real-time processing.

We evaluated the time required to perform the C2PA generation and embedding. For that, we also consider two different storage devices, an SD card (SanDisk Extreme 1TB) and an SSD (Micron 2550 NVMe SSD 256GB). The SD card offers read and write speeds of 160 MB/s and 90 MB/s, respectively, while the SSD provides 4500 MB/s and 2000 MB/s. Despite the SSD’s significantly higher speed, the connection to the Raspberry Pi is over PCIe Gen 3 with a single lane. This limits the maximum theoretical speed to 1000 MB/s. The results, shown in Table V, were obtained using two video files of 3 seconds and 10 seconds with the C2PA embedding process repeated 100 times for each case under the same conditions. As seen, the time difference is negligible for short videos, with only a 0.28% improvement when using the SSD. However, the SSD significantly reduces timing deviations, resulting in better predictability and reduced jitter, which is an important factor for real-time video transmission. This indicates a potential bottleneck in the device’s CPU or the C2PA SDK, likely caused by how the latter one reads the file from disk, calculates the hash and signature and writes the file back. Therefore, future optimization of the C2PA SDK may be necessary to fully support live use cases, though such improvements are not yet part of the current specification.

Last, testing was performed to evaluate the end-to-end latency, scalability, stability and robustness of the C2PA enabled live video system. The testing has been performed using Full HD video at 30 fps, which is the quality commonly used

for live streaming. The devices used for testing were running locally and connected over WiFi to the same network. Do note that the RPi 5 does not contain specialized hardware for live streaming (it even lacks HW support for video encoding), so higher delay than the one that could be obtained with real professional hardware is expected. Do also note that in HLS (and considering the applications in mind like YouTube or Twitch), there is usually some artificially added delay: if something against the T&S of the platform happens, the streamer can remove or pause the stream without facing a penalty. Generally the video player at the client side also adds some delay to the live stream, as they do not play back for the user the last video segment that is being downloaded. This is done to make the experience smoother for the user, ensuring that some subsequent fragments are available before loading and playing them to avoid buffering or sudden cutoffs. With regards to end to end latency, the minimum achievable latency was measured as the delay from video capture in the server till the video is shown with the C2PA information in the client. The whole pipeline introduces around 5.3 ± 0.4 s of delay with a 3 s fragment length in HLS. A value of 4.1 ± 0.3 s was obtained without the C2PA addition, approximately 1s less than the C2PA enabled pipeline. The delay goes down to 2.5 ± 0.1 s when a 1s fragment size is being used in a Raspberry Pi 5 (1.4 ± 0.1 s without the addition of C2PA). In order to improve the timing when the C2PA is being embedded onto the video pipeline, the logic to add the C2PA metadata was modified and refined. With this, 1.7 ± 0.3 s was obtained with a 1 second segment length, and 3.9 ± 0.4 s with a 3 seconds segment length, which closely matches the non-C2PA pipeline. This shows that the C2PA addition does indeed not add significant delay to the processing of the video. Note that similar timings were obtained with a Lenovo ThinkPad laptop with a TPM, so this time seems independent from the device used. To measure the scalability, 30 different HLS sessions across 3 different devices were simulated by using different browser windows to connect to the C2PA enabled HLS stream. The server was able to serve the video with the C2PA information to all clients simultaneously without a problem. This number could even be further increased up to 100.000 concurrent users with the chosen Go server implementation, however it would require more RAM memory than the one available with the Raspberry Pi [52]. In terms of playback stability under load, we stress-tested the Raspberry Pi by running the necessary software for the C2PA-enabled live stream, then artificially increasing the CPU utilization to 100%. After 10 minutes of testing at room temperature, the RPi's temperature rose by 40 degrees with active cooling. However, no increase in delay or frame drops was detected. Last, regarding robustness, given that the low power hardware used based on the Raspberry Pi 5 is already capable of providing the service, it is expected that a more mature platform like Twitch or YouTube Live could provide this service with an even better quality for the users.

VI. INTEGRATION OPPORTUNITIES

Currently, the C2PA specification mainstream support is mainly focused on static images, like in LinkedIn, or for static

videos, like in YouTube. Since the C2PA SDK was used to generate and embed the manifest, any fragment of the live video produced by our implementation is expected to validate correctly and display the associated information when used in a future compatible application. The implemented C2PA live video streaming service over HLS can be extended to many existing live video platforms that support HLS, such as X (formerly known as Twitter) and YouTube Live [53] [54]. These platforms allow direct HLS video retransmission from the source, enabling streamers to encode their own HLS video and embed the C2PA manifest into video fragments. This would provide viewers with a way to authenticate that the stream originates from a trusted source, while minimal changes to the user interface would be required to display the validation status for each video fragment, as shown in Fig. 5. In the case of YouTube, C2PA information can already be provided in the video description, but only for already uploaded videos and not for live streams [5]. Regarding Twitch, which is by far the most popular live-streaming platform, it does not allow streamers to send HLS video directly to its servers. Instead, the architecture of Twitch, as shown in Fig. 10, uses a combination of Real Time Messaging Protocol (RTMP) and HLS to reduce latency to only a couple of seconds. In this case, streamers send their video over RTMP to the nearest Point of Presence (PoP) where Twitch processes and converts it to HLS for playback, resulting in delays of only a few seconds. Each stream is uniquely identified by the streamer's key, ensuring a level of authentication within Twitch's ecosystem.

When the Twitch infrastructure receives the video over RTMP in the PoP, it can be sent to the Origins (powerful data centers that are in charge of processing the video) and decoding and encoding it into HLS with different resolutions and qualities to ensure that all users can access the stream, regardless of their internet connection quality. Additionally, the Twitch architecture is designed to scale for many concurrent users and bypasses restrictions such as proxy blocks that could affect RTP traffic [55]. In this setup, the Twitch architecture itself could handle the addition of C2PA information to HLS fragments at the Origins, identifying the necessary information to add by the streamer's unique and secret Key. In that case, the C2PA manifest should avoid including personal or location information to protect the privacy of streamers. On the other end, the Twitch native or web application could validate the manifest in each video fragment and display its status in the user interface, as shown in the mock-up of Fig. 11. Finally, although this approach offers media provenance, it would also greatly benefit from increased security. RTMP streams are sent over HTTP without encryption, making it possible for an attacker on the same local network to intercept the stream key and hijack the stream. To achieve a fully secure and authenticated C2PA live stream on Twitch, RTMP should be upgraded to secure RTMP (RTMPS), which uses TLS/SSL to encrypt the connection. Implementing mutual TLS (mTLS) to verify both the server and client would reduce significantly the risk of stream hijacking.

Fig. 10. Simplified Twitch backbone architecture.

Fig. 11. Mock-up of C2PA integration in Twitch.

VII. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a live video streaming system with media provenance and authenticity was developed based on the C2PA specification. Both the client and server were implemented. The server generates live video segments with embedded C2PA manifests relying on a hardware-based Trusted Platform Module (TPM), while the client's backend downloads these segments, verifies the manifest and presents the validation status and metadata using a Content Credentials-based pop-up in the graphical user interface. The results demonstrate that the addition of the C2PA manifest introduces minimal overhead to the video file size, even for short video segments, ensuring it does not significantly affect live video playback or transmission. The timing measurements for signature generation using the TPM revealed that, when properly optimized with persistent key storage, the delay introduced is low enough to be compatible with live streaming. Further experiments confirmed that the C2PA embedding time is not significantly influenced by the storage media. Although improvements in storage media such as SSDs reduce variability and jitter, the performance bottleneck lies in the current C2PA SDK implementation, which may require future optimizations to fully support real-time applications. Practical implementation examples were

explored, highlighting how this system could be integrated into major live streaming platforms such as YouTube Live or Twitch. Overall, this work provides a practical alternative for implementing verifiable live video streams with minimal impact on performance and file size, paving the way for greater transparency and trust in live media content.

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